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Geophysical Investigation of Road Failure in Parts of Anambra Sedimentary Basin using Integrated Electrical Methods: A Case Study of Nsukka, Southeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Objectives: To delineate the primary causes of road failure in the Nsukka sedimentary basin southeast Nigeria by defining the geoelectric and geologic characteristics of the subsurface. **Method:** Vertical electrical sounding (VES) and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) surveys using Schlumberger and Wenner electrode configurations were employed respectively in this survey. WinResist and Res2DINV software were used to evaluate the fifteen VES and four ERT profiles that were collected from the highway's stable and failing sections. ORIGIN software was used to contour the computed values. **Findings:** Five to six geoelectric layers, with resistivity values between 40.4 and 73,324.3 Ωm and thicknesses between 0.7 and 174.3 m, are identified. Stable portions have much greater resistivity, suggesting competent, well-drained sandy formations, while failed sections are typically underlain by low-resistivity (<500 Ωm) clay-rich, water-saturated strata within the top 50 m. Low-resistivity zones are identified as stand-ins for weak subgrade conditions by the establishment of a quantitative resistivity to competence connection. **Novelty:** The study shows that 1D VES and 2D ERT may be used to resolve lateral heterogeneity and vertical stratification, offering a reliable, predictive framework for mapping failure risks and assessing subgrade integrity in sedimentary terrains.

Keywords: Road failure; Geomaterial; Electrical Resistivity; VES; ERT

1 Introduction

Road transportation plays a vital role in Nigeria's socioeconomic development, yet many highways experience premature failures such as rutting, cracking, potholes, sinkholes, and subsidence long before their design life. Although inadequate drainage, inferior materials, and traffic loads are frequently blamed, these theories are nevertheless insufficient to explain the ongoing and spatially varied degradation seen throughout southeast Nigeria that impose economic losses, increase maintenance demands, and compromise transportation safety^{(1), (2)}. Pavement instability and collapse are mostly caused by weak, clay-rich, water-saturated subsurface layers that are frequently linked to low resistivity and poor bearing capacity, according to recent geophysical investigations^{(3), (4)}.

Many investigations depend on single approaches, such as VES or 2D resistivity imaging, which intrinsically give partial subsurface characterization⁽⁴⁾. Even in cases where integrated techniques are tried, they frequently just combine datasets without fully using their complimentary qualities⁽⁵⁾. Identifying low-resistivity zones (clay or saturated layers) and deriving higher-order geoelectric parameters such as resistivity, porosity, anisotropy and hydraulic conductance becomes paramount^{(6), (7)}. Previous research typically yields interpretations that are descriptive rather than predictive, providing little direction for engineering design, failure prevention, or long-term rehabilitation tactics⁽⁸⁾. Together, these flaws cause subsurface models to be fragmented, underestimated heterogeneity, and reoccur failure even after remediation^{(5), (9)}.

This study presents an integrated multi-scale geophysical framework for investigating road failure within the Nsukka sedimentary basin using VES and ERT. By combining multi-method imaging with quantitative evaluation of hydraulic conductance, anisotropy, and porosity, the study improves heterogeneity characterization, and weak foundation zones. Unlike conventional resistivity-based studies that rely mainly on qualitative interpretation, this work establishes quantitative resistivity thresholds for distinguishing failed and stable pavement sections and integrates geophysical data with field observations such as flooding, sinkholes and cracks. The result will identify the hydrogeological conditions controlling pavement instability along the Aloruno–Obukpa–Obollo Afor and Aloruno–Okpuje–Idah highways, thereby providing a more predictive approach for road failure assessment, remediation, and sustainable infrastructure development. Figure 1 illustrates some of the failing sections of the roadways under study.

Fig 1. Parallel flat flood plains, a sinkhole on the road, Failed/ unstable segment of the road

1.1 The Geology of the Study Area

The two primary geological formations in the study area are the Ajali sandstone and the Nsukka formation, which are found in parts of Nsukka and Udenu L.G.A. of Enugu state. The distribution of the formations within the study area is depicted in Figure 2. The Ajali sandstone, within the middle-upper Maastrichtian age exhibits a varying thickness of less than 300m to over 1000m at the centre of the basin⁽¹⁰⁾. The landscape is extremely undulating, with height observed in the field ranging from 281 to 521 meters above sea level^{(11), (12)}. The Nsukka formation contains an alternation of fine-grain sandstone, sandy and dark grey shale which correspond to periods of flooding and normal sedimentation. The sediments pile across the entire basin with a layer thickness ranging from 75 m to over 1000 m⁽¹³⁾.

2 Methodology

Geophysical investigations were conducted using the ABEM Terrameter SAS 1000 with Schlumberger (VES) and Wenner (ERT) electrode configurations to obtain complementary subsurface information. Fifteen VES stations were obtained across failed and

Fig 2. Geologic Map Showing the Sounding Points

stable highway sections, including major failure zones along the Obukpa–Ovoko and Aloruno–Okpuje–Idah axes, while VES 12 and VES 13 served as control sites representing stable subsurface conditions. WinRESIST and RES2DINV software were used for data processing and interpretation. The final geoelectric parameters were obtained via partial curve matching, smoothing, and iterative forward modeling approaches. The ORIGIN software program was also employed to produce contour maps and 3D graphs. The apparent resistivity (ρ_a) is computed using Equation 1⁽¹⁴⁾:

$$\rho_a = \pi \cdot \left[\frac{\left(\frac{AB}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{MN}{2}\right)^2}{MN} \right] R_a \tag{1}$$

$$\rho_a = G_s \cdot R_a \tag{2}$$

where G_s is the geometric factor : $\pi \cdot \left[\frac{\left(\frac{AB}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{MN}{2}\right)^2}{MN} \right]$ and R_a is the apparent resistance.

The hydraulic conductivity, porosity, of layers 1, 2, 3 were determined using the primary parameters (thickness and resistivity). The resistivities and thicknesses were added up to obtain the bulk resistivity ρ_B and thickness h_B employed for our analysis. The free flow of groundwater in a porous material is called hydraulic conductivity (K). Hydraulic conductivity was calculated using Equation 3⁽¹⁵⁾:

$$K = \frac{386.40}{\rho_B^{0.93282}} \tag{3}$$

where ρ , is the resistivity of the aquifer or overlying layers.

Coefficient of Anisotropy refers to the directional variation of soil or rock properties which accurately predicts soil strength, deformation, and drainage behavior, thereby improving pavement design and reducing risks of cracking and premature road failure⁽¹⁶⁾.

$$C. \text{ Anisotropy} = \frac{LR}{TR} \tag{4}$$

where Longitudinal resistivity

$$LR = (\rho_B \times h_B) \times (h_B \div \rho_B) \tag{5}$$

and Transverse resistivity

$$TR = (\rho_B \times h_B) \div h_B \tag{6}$$

The reflection coefficient (RC) measures the contrasts in seismic or acoustic impedance between subsurface layers and identifies the variations in soil strength and weak pavement zones⁽¹⁷⁾. High RCs indicate transitions from rigid to soft or water-saturated layers⁽¹⁸⁾, resulting to differential settlement and pavement failure⁽¹⁹⁾. Low RCs, however, reflect more stable homogeneous subsurface conditions. RC is estimated using **Equations 7-8**

$$RC_{LAYER1} = \frac{h_1}{\rho_1}, \quad RC_{LAYER2} = \frac{h_2}{\rho_2}, \quad RC_{LAYER3} = \frac{h_3}{\rho_3} \tag{7}$$

Bulk Long. Resistance LR_B was estimated using Equation

$$LR_B = \frac{h_B}{RC_B} \tag{8}$$

where h and h_B are thickness and bulk thickness.

Porosity (ϕ_B) measures the void spaces within rocks or soils and determines their water-holding capacity. Highly porous soils retain water, weaken subgrade strength, and promote pavement deformation or erosion. The effective porosity is calculated using **equation 4**⁽¹²⁾.

$$\phi_B = 25.5 + 4.5 \ln K_B \tag{9}$$

where K_B is the hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer or overlying layer.

For 2D imaging, the Wenner array was employed along four 250 m longitudinal profiles and one 600 m transverse profile across severely distressed road sections. Electrode spacing of 10–40 m were used to optimize depth penetration and resolution. Field data were processed with RES2DINV software to generate 2D resistivity pseudo-sections. The apparent resistivity is given by

$$\rho_a = 2\pi \cdot \frac{\Delta v}{I} a \tag{11}$$

where a is the electrodes spacing and $\frac{\Delta v}{I} = R$ is the measured resistance.

3 Results and Discussion

VES data were processed and modelled using WinResist software in accordance with standard smoothing and curve-matching procedures. A summary of the interpreted results (Table 1) shows resistivity, depth, thickness, and curve types across all profiles within the maximum electrode separation. This study offers a systematic multi-layer quantitative comparison between failed and stable road segments, allowing for a clearer discrimination of subsurface conditions responsible for pavement instability, in contrast to many previous studies in similar sedimentary terrains that only rely on qualitative curve interpretation or single-layer resistivity classification^{(2), (4)}.

The resistivity values of the first geoelectric layer (topsoil), which is mostly formed of clay to sandy-silt, range from 40.4 Ω m to 1841.1 Ω m, with thicknesses ranging from 0.5 m to 3.9 m. The resistivity of the second layer (clay-silt-sand mixture) varies between 108.8 Ω m and 11730.1 Ω m, with a thickness range of 2.1 m to 20.4 m. This study demonstrates that failed zones are typically characterized by reduced resistivity signatures, suggesting increased compressibility and water sensitivity. In

a similar vein, the resistivity of the third layer (fine to medium sand) vary from 264.8 Ωm to 73324.3 Ωm , with failed segments showing significantly smaller resistivity ranges (264.8–8025 Ωm) than stable segments (3089.5–73324.3 Ωm). This study clearly shows that failing parts constantly show much lower resistivity. The resistivity values of the fourth layer (medium to coarse sand), which mostly corresponds to aquifer-bearing layers, range from 1467.3 Ωm to 58535.7 Ωm . Stable zones (9534.3–58535.7 Ωm) regularly display higher values than failed zones (1467.3–23075.3 Ωm . The stable road segments show noticeably greater resistivity signatures associated with silt, sand, and gravel, whereas failing road segments are consistently linked to low resistivity values associated with clay⁽²⁰⁾.

Table 1. Summary of resistivity survey results from computer modeling using WINRESIST software

S/N	VES points	Longitude Latitude ($^{\circ} N$)		Resistivity (Ωm)						Thickness (m)					Depth (m)					Curve Type
		($^{\circ} E$)		ρ_1	ρ_2	ρ_3	ρ_4	ρ_5	ρ_6	h_1	h_2	h_3	h_4	h_5	d_1	d_2	d_3	d_4	d_5	
1	Obukpa	7.4245	6.8814	143.3	282.3	1379.8	13527.1	14013.6	-	3.2	9.4	22.5	123.2	-	3.2	12.6	35.1	158.3	-	AAA
2	Ibeku-Ovoko	7.4373	6.8847	261.9	1138.4	496.1	1467.3	8037.5	4598.6	1.3	6.0	3.6	25.0	76.0	1.3	7.4	11.0	35.9	112.0	KHAK
3	Isiuja-Ovoko	7.4663	6.8931	200.8	478.6	8104.3	22417.6	10843.9	-	3.9	2.8	22.2	153.5	-	3.9	6.6	28.9	182.3	-	AAK
4	Likke - Iheaka	7.4802	6.9003	342.5	748.2	3738.0	12121.6	10727.3	-	2.0	9.0	32.7	146.9	-	2.0	11.2	43.9	190.7	-	AAK
5	Obollo-Afor	7.5005	6.9093	355.5	3657.6	8025	23075.3	8575.8	-	3.1	19.5	22.8	121.0	-	3.1	22.6	45.4	166.4	-	AAK
6	AGbamere Eha-Alumona	7.4546	6.8275	1193.7	300.2	13791.4	58535.7	7879.2	-	2.8	5.2	10.9	133.0	-	2.8	8.0	18.9	152.0	-	HAK
7	Umuabo Eha-Alumona I	7.4523	6.8203	357.3	717.1	1850.5	5072.8	7960.6	-	2.4	5.1	74.8	111.9	-	2.4	7.5	82.3	194.2	-	AAA
8	Eha - Alumona	7.4543	6.8161	857.7	1822.2	17967.0	2762.6	312.8	-	2.2	12.6	42.8	56.3	-	2.2	14.7	57.5	113.8	-	AKQ
9	Umuabo Eha - Alumona II	7.4500	6.8104	836.6	1665.9	3542.2	6835.1	663.6	-	2.5	7.7	31.6	94.0	-	2.5	10.3	41.9	135.9	-	AAK
10	Ede-Oballa	7.4286	6.8010	60.3	1141.6	1106.2	8270.7	3208.2	-	0.6	20.4	23.3	133.7	-	0.6	20.9	44.2	178.0	-	KHK
11	Ama - Ezike	7.4194	6.8036	40.4	11730.1	73324.3	3473.0	1328.5	-	0.5	2.1	30.4	85.8	-	0.5	2.6	33.1	118.9	-	AKQ
12	Tech College Amogwu	7.3543	6.8543	1841.1	3364.5	3089.5	17309.2	957.3	-	1.1	9.9	23.9	84.6	-	1.1	11.0	34.9	199.6	-	KHK
13	Army Barracks Nsukka	7.3649	6.8515	1614.6	3511.8	16591.8	9534.3	954.7	-	3.0	20.2	55.8	67.4	-	3.0	23.2	79.1	146.5	-	AKQ
14	Alor-Uno I	7.3837	6.8692	341.5	1149.6	3364.3	17419.6	442.0	-	0.8	17.9	13.1	61.5	-	0.8	18.7	31.8	93.2	-	AAK
15	Alor-Uno II	7.3714	6.8877	216.2	108.8	264.8	29812	1710.3	-	0.8	3.6	36.3	157.8	-	0.8	4.4	40.7	198.5	-	HAK

A plot showing the variation in resistivity of the first three geoelectric layer across the VES locations where most of road construction processes takes place is presented in Figure 3. Layer 1 (topsoil) shows moderate to high resistivity values, where low resistivity zones indicate clayey, water-saturated soils with poor drainage and weak foundation conditions, while higher resistivity values suggest lateritic or sandy soils suitable for pavement support. The second layer (subgrade) displays low resistivity zones corresponding to clayey or highly weathered materials prone to deformation, swelling, and shrinkage, thereby contributing to pavement failure, especially during heavy rainfall and increased water infiltration. Layer 3 generally exhibits higher resistivity values, indicating relatively competent materials such as compacted sandy layers or partially weathered rock. The resistivity variations therefore help identify critical zones requiring engineering interventions such as soil stabilization, drainage improvement, and replacement of weak subgrade materials.

Fig 3. Plots showing the variations of resistivities of layer 1, 2, and 3

3.1 Calculated Parameters

The calculated subsurface parameters for layers 1–3, presented in Table 2 and Figure 4, indicate that failed road sections are mainly associated with low resistivity, high porosity, and moisture-rich clayey materials, reflecting weak subgrade conditions. In contrast, control sites such as Tech College and Army Barracks exhibit high resistivity, low hydraulic conductivity, and low porosity, indicating more competent and stable subsurface materials. Areas with relatively higher hydraulic conductivity also correspond to increased porosity, suggesting enhanced fluid movement and reduced soil strength⁽²¹⁾.

Anisotropy value ranges from 0.17 to 0.60 showing an underlying variability (Figure 5). Low-anisotropy zones show a homogeneous, water-saturated clayey materials with high vulnerability to pavement deformation and failure while moderate-to-high anisotropy zones suggests a more compacted and heterogeneous formations with improved drainage and load-bearing ability. The findings support the usefulness of anisotropy analysis in determining weak subgrade zones and assessing the integrity of road foundations⁽²²⁾. RC analysis presented in Figure ??, revealed that K_1 values (first–second layer contrast) were mostly positive (0.3–1.1), with high values at VES 5, 11, and 12 indicating competent and well-drained subsurface materials, while a negative value at VES 6 suggests conductive, weak underlying layers. K_2 values (second–third layer contrast) ranged from about –0.2 to 1.0 and showed greater variability, with negative values at VES 10 indicating saturated and unstable subgrade conditions. Generally, high positive K_1 and K_2 values correspond to stable lateritic or sandy formations suitable for road construction, whereas low or negative values indicate clay-rich, water-saturated, and compressible materials associated with road failure and subgrade instability.

The 2D resistivity images generated with RES2DINV revealed subsurface geoelectric variations beneath the investigated road sections. Pseudo-Section 1, located at Ibigbe Obukpa near VES 1, 2, and 15, showed an undulating topsoil layer with resistivity values ranging from 330 to 1400 Ω m and thicknesses of about 1.25–12.4 m. The ERT 2D inverted resistivity model (pseudo-

Table 2. Calculated parameters for Layer 1, 2 & 3 from its resistivity and thickness values

S/N	VES Station	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Overlying Resistivity Layer (1,2&3) $\rho_B (\Omega m)$	Overlying thickness Layer (1,2&3) $h_B (m)$	Overlying Hydraulic conductivity $K_B (\Omega^{-1})$	Overlying Porosity (φ_B)	Layer 1 Reflection coefficient (K1)	Layer 2 Reflection coefficient (K2)	Layer 3 Reflection coefficient (K3)	Bulk Transverse Resistivity ($\rho^T B$)	Bulk Longitudinal Resistivity (ρ_L)	Coefficient of Anisotropy (λ)
1	Obukpa	7.4245	6.8814	1805.4	35.1	0.3542	20.8291	0.3266	0.6603	0.8149	1805.4	487.9378	0.5199
2	Ibeku-Ovoko	7.4373	6.8847	1896.4	10.9	0.3383	20.6226	0.6259	-0.3929	0.4947	1896.4	623.1818	0.5732
3	Isiuja-Ovoko	7.4663	6.8931	8783.7	28.9	0.0810	14.1878	0.4089	0.8885	0.4690	8783.7	1031.7010	0.3427
4	Likke-Iheaka	7.4802	6.9003	4828.7	43.7	0.1415	16.6993	0.3720	0.6664	0.5286	4828.7	1641.8520	0.5831
5	Obollo-Afor	7.5005	6.9093	12038.1	45.4	0.0603	12.8647	0.8228	0.3738	0.4839	12038.1	2687.5680	0.4725
6	AGbamere Eha Alu-mona	7.4546	6.8275	15285.3	18.9	0.0483	11.8622	-0.5981	0.9574	0.6186	15285.3	923.8539	0.2459
7	Umuabo Eha-Alumona I	7.4523	6.8203	2924.9	82.3	0.2258	18.8037	0.3349	0.4414	0.4654	2924.9	1517.0360	0.7202
8	Eha – Alu-mona	7.4543	6.8161	20646.9	57.6	0.0365	10.6001	0.3599	0.8158	-0.7335	20646.9	4855.8980	0.4850
9	Umuabo Eha – Alu-mona II	7.4500	6.8104	6044.7	41.8	0.1147	15.7565	0.3314	0.3603	0.3173	6044.7	2528.5180	0.6468
10	Ede-Oballa	7.4286	6.8010	2308.1	44.3	0.2816	19.7979	0.8997	-0.0158	0.7641	2308.1	906.2454	0.6266
11	Ama – Ezike	7.4194	6.8036	85094.8	33	0.0097	4.6553	0.9931	0.7242	-0.9096	85094.8	2544.3600	0.1729
12	Tech College Amogwu	7.3543	6.8543	8295.1	34.9	0.0854	14.4280	0.2927	-0.0426	0.6971	8295.1	3095.1140	0.6108
13	Army Barracks Nsukka	7.3649	6.8515	21718.2	79	0.0348	10.3877	0.3701	0.6506	-0.2701	21718.2	7199.3660	0.5757
14	Alor-Uno I	7.3837	6.8692	4855.4	31.8	0.1407	16.6762	0.5420	0.4906	0.6763	4855.4	1458.2430	0.5480
15	Alor-Uno II	7.3714	6.8877	589.8	40.7	1.0056	25.5253	-0.3305	0.4176	0.8369	589.8	234.0788	0.6300

Fig 4. 2D/3D contour maps showing variation of overlying hydraulic conductivity and porosity of layer 1, 2 & 3

Fig 5. 2D/3D contour maps showing variation of overlying C. Anisotropy of layer 1, 2 & 3; Plot showing the variations of reflection coefficients K1 and K2

section 2) in Figure 6 near VES 5 at Obollo-Afor reveals a heterogeneous subsurface with significant resistivity contrasts. A shallow low-resistivity zone (3.2–45 Ωm) between 100–185 m lateral distances indicate water-saturated, clay-rich lateritic or weathered materials associated with weak subgrade conditions. The presence of shallow conductive, water-saturated materials likely contributes to road deterioration, since resistivity decreases with increasing moisture and clay content, which weakens subgrade integrity⁽¹⁶⁾. The pseudo-section for Profile 3 at Lejja, near VES 10 and VES 11, revealed a thin top layer of low-to-moderate resistivity materials (160–1824 Ωm) with thicknesses ranging from 1.25 to 9.8 m, indicating clay-rich formations. Highly resistive zones (28835–70423 Ωm), interpreted as weathered and unsaturated basement materials, were observed at depths of approximately 9.8–39.4 m which may contribute to sinkholes and pavement cracking. Pseudo-Section 4, located near VES 12 and VES 13 in Nsukka, a potential alternative road route to the Okpuje-Idah highway. The inverted model revealed a thick (Figure 6), highly resistive top layer (1409–2508 Ωm) with thicknesses of about 1.25–13 m, indicating competent and impermeable materials suitable for road and foundation construction. Beneath this lies a moderately resistive layer (250–791

Ωm), interpreted as freshly weathered gneiss, with thickness increasing south-eastward and an identified deeper conductive zone with low resistivity (44.3–140 Ωm).

Fig 6. Sample ERT pseudo-section for profile 2 (VES 5 stable part) and profile 4 close to (VES 12 and 13 stable/control part)

4 Conclusion

The integrated application of VES and ERT successfully delineated the geoelectric characteristics responsible for the recurrent road failures along the Aloruno–Obukpa and Aloruno–Okpuje–Idah highway axis. Quantitative interpretation of the resistivity models showed that the failed road segments are characterized by water-saturated sandy lateritic/clayey materials that extend from the surface to depths close to 40 meters, high conductivity, elevated porosity, and consistently low resistivity values (<100–300 Ωm). In contrast, the stable sections exhibited significantly higher resistivity values (>1000 Ωm), suggesting underlying materials that were less permeable, more competent, and compacted. The ERT pseudo-sections further revealed that the failed zones are underlain by thick weathered clay-rich formations with poor drainage capacity and high moisture retention, conditions that promote weakening of the pavement foundation and progressive deformation under traffic loading.

This study characterized the stable and failing pavement sections within the Nsukka sedimentary environment and quantitatively demonstrated the association between low resistivity, high porosity, saturation, and pavement instability, in contrast to earlier research that mostly relied on single-method investigations or qualitative studies. According to the geophysical evidence, the subgrade materials that are incompetent should be excavated and replaced, if possible, with mechanically stable and impermeable fill materials down to a depth of about 40 meters. Adequate drainage systems should also be installed to minimize water infiltration. In order to establish regional correlations between lithology, resistivity signatures, and pavement performance, future research should focus on other roads in the Nsukka sedimentary basin and similar geologic environments throughout Nigeria. These regional datasets would aid in the creation of geophysical suitability maps for highway

construction and sustainable infrastructure planning. Finally, the study confirms that integrated resistivity methods offer a dependable, non-invasive, and economical method for assessing subgrade competence and for preventing future highway failures in sedimentary terrain.

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6 Author contributions

Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Jude Chukwuebuka Ugwu, Johnson Cletus Ibuot, Nyakno Jimmy George: Conceptualization and Research design. Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Jude Chukwuebuka Ugwu, Johnson Cletus Ibuot, Nyakno Jimmy George: Field data acquisition and analysis. Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Johnson Cletus Ibuot, Nyakno Jimmy George: Methodology, data interpretation and manuscript writing. Ngozi Mirianrita Ugwu, Jude Chukwuebuka Ugwu, Johnson Cletus Ibuot, Nyakno Jimmy George: Reviewing, Editing and Supervision.

7 Data availability

The data used in this manuscript will be made available if requested for.

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